

ANALYSIS OF QUALIFICATION REQUIREMENTS, CURRICULA, AND TEXTBOOKS FOR 2ND-COURSE STUDENTS AT HIGHER EDUCATION

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The main document containing training requirements for students and recommendations for their teaching of foreign languages is the Qualification requirements for the Bachelor's degree program in Foreign Language and Literature-60111800: English Language, approved by the order №344 of August 8, 2023-year of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This Qualification requirements for the Bachelor's degree program in Foreign Language and Literature-60111800 includes the following sections:

1. Foreign Language and Literature: English Language-General description of the Bachelor's Degree Program
2. Requirements for professional competencies of bachelor's degree holders in the 60111800-Foreign Language and Literature: English language program

The analysis of the section 1.2.4. Professional duties of bachelor's degree holders in this program reveal that according to the National Qualification Framework, Level 6, and in alignment with the fields, objects, and types of professional activities associated with 60111800-Foreign Language and Literature: English Language bachelor's program, a graduate must be capable of performing the following professional duties:

In Pedagogical Activity:

While planning the learning process, a graduate must be able to develop a curriculum according to the goals of State Educational Standards (SES) and educational programs, adapt educational programs based on students' needs and interests, design lesson plans according to specific lesson objectives and expected outcomes, plan teaching methods and formats using a differentiated approach, plan the use of instructional, visual, and handout materials.

The next section is titled "To ensure the effectiveness of education in pedagogical performance" a student in this direction should be able to set tasks based on lesson objectives and students' capabilities, use demonstration and handout materials appropriate to the lesson topic, plan effective time management during the lesson, make efficient use of information

and Communication Technologies (ICT) in the educational process, organize lessons based on students' learning outcomes and analyze the effectiveness of teaching approaches, select teaching methods and strategies that align with students' educational goals and age characteristics, using active teaching methods, apply approaches aimed at developing students' core competencies and life skills, organize students' group and project-based work, promote self-assessment skills, provide differentiated support to students, ensure the integration of theory and practice, create opportunities for students to develop independent thinking, achieve motivation during the lesson, facilitate effective communication in the classroom.

While compiling the themes for Phenomenon-based learning, we have taken into account the list of requirements in the section titled Pedagogical Performance in which a graduate must be able to acquire core competencies and life skills. One of the objectives of Phenomenon-based learning is reflected in the development of life skills and core competencies such as Personal skills (self-awareness, self-management, resilience), Interpersonal skills (Communication, teamwork, and empathy), thinking skills (critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making), practical life skills (time management), digital literacy (using technology safely and effectively). Also, the themes integrated with the Phenomenon-based approach facilitate learners not only to acquire a theoretical basis of the theme but also exposed to the practical side of it. A learner can see, observe, and sense a real phenomenon demanding a tangible solution from them. This process will ultimately urge them to think independently and achieve motivation during the lesson, a key element in a deep learning process.

In the next section titled "To Assess Learning and Provide Feedback, a graduate must be able to use various methods and tools to assess learning outcomes, employ diverse methods and tools to diagnose educational results, analyze students' learning outcomes, use the results of analysis to adjust lesson plans and teaching methods, know and effectively apply assessment criteria in practice, identify and analyze existing problems in the learning process.

The following section supports the idea that a graduate must be able to use various methods and tools to detect educational results and analyze their learning outcomes. The themes integrated with the Phenomenon-based learning approach facilitate learners to find effective solutions to the relevant educational problems. During this process, they will have an opportunity to apply different methods to find a solution by analyzing whether their

solutions will work in the process. Also, while working with specific issue, it is possible they can come across additional educational matters demanding further research with an effective measure. As one of the key principles of the Phenomenon-based learning approach states that the learning process should stimulate life-long learning.

Regarding the section titled “Scientific-research performance” a graduate must be able to conduct research in scientific institutions and research centers in the field of English language and literature on topics related to subject content and teaching methodology, purposefully search for and identifying the latest scientific achievements related to English language and literature on the internet, and directly applying them in practice, study scientific collections and both local and international research findings related to the methodology of teaching English and subject-specific areas, prepare scientific research projects and participating in the evaluation of literature and scholarly works in the field, collect, process, and systematically analyze scientific information on specific topics, possess the ability to apply research results and developments in the field of English language and literature.

The primary aim of this section is to encourage students to acquire research skills. Specifically, the ability to work with the scientific materials, analyze their contents to select the appropriate ones, synthesize the authors’ ideas, and apply research results relevant to their chosen field is an essential part of the learning process. Completing all these procedures without the assistance of teachers will help them be independent and self-reliant learners capable of managing their research work.

In the next section titled “In Spiritual and Educational Activities”, it is stated that a graduate must be able to know the methods and technologies for developing students’ immunity against ideological and informational attacks.

The processes of analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating the content claim to safeguard learners from ideologies and encourage forming immunity against informational attacks.

The section titled “ Organizational and Managerial Activity” states that a graduate must be able to develop mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating the quality of the educational process using pedagogical and information technologies, organize and manage social, spiritual, and educational activities within a team, make sound decisions in situations involving diverse opinions; have the ability to develop a work plan related to their professional activities, monitor its implementation, and evaluate the outcomes of the work performed.

This section aimed at facilitating a learning process in which a learner can organize educational activities involved in learning and manage the tasks while working in a team and having the capacity to make workable decisions, and organize a learning process leading to tangible outcomes, and be responsible to the whole learning process. These all processes are supposed to be reflected in the themes based on the key principles of the Phenomenon-based approach.

2. Requirements for Professional Competencies of Bachelor's Degree Holders in 60111800 – Foreign Language and Literature (English Language and Literature)

The main aim of the subsection titled “General Competencies” is the instilling the skills for personal development, the ability to self-assess objectively, and to enhance the intellectual development of learners, effectively apply the core principles and methods of general and specialized disciplines in addressing social and professional tasks, express thoughts clearly and systematically in the native language, work with academic texts, and demonstrate written and oral communication skills in either the native or a foreign language for public speaking purposes, utilize methods, techniques, and tools for gathering, filtering, storing, and processing information, and demonstrate media literacy and skills in working with global computer networks, understand the principles of conducting scientific research and achieve scientific knowledge, demonstrate the ability to maintain a healthy lifestyle in accordance with hygiene, occupational safety, and environmental protection standards.

In the next section titled “Professional Competencies” a graduate must be able to have the ability to model the educational and upbringing process and apply it in teaching practice, be proficient in organizing collaborative and interpersonal interaction among participants in the educational process, the ability to implement interdisciplinary integration in solving professional tasks, as well as ensuring the integration, continuity, and harmony between theory and practice, mastery of critical thinking methodologies, ensure technical safety in English language and literature classes, possessing a value-based attitude toward inclusive education, familiarity with hospital pedagogy technologies for working with students requiring long-term treatment, capability to deliver outcome-oriented and mobility-focused instruction that helps learners develop competencies for adapting to a changing labor market and fosters the development of an active civic position. The primary purpose of this section entails learners to be proficient at working collaboratively while accomplishing educational tasks and implementing theoretical knowledge in practice by integrating several disciplines

into one to know different professional perspectives concerning the discussed topic. These all capacities acquired in the learning process can prepare professionals who can meet the demands of the current and future labor market.

The analysis of the program of Integration of Language Skills has revealed that the purposes and tasks of this module are as follows:

- to teach students the integrated use of oral and written forms of the language;
- to develop communication skills in various contexts, particularly to improve their practical and theoretical knowledge of the foreign language being learned;
- to ensure that they can confidently apply the acquired knowledge, skills, and competencies in their professional and academic activities.

The module is aimed at developing communication skills to ensure the application of acquired knowledge, skills, and competencies in their academic careers.

The objective of the subject is to teach the necessary language skills in an integrated manner and to develop communication competencies so that students can achieve a B2+ level proficiency in the foreign language being studied, according to the internationally recognized standards.

Table 2.1

Outcomes of mastering the subject	Teaching technologies and methods
Attain B2+ level proficiency in the foreign language according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR)	Working in groups and pairs
Acquire speaking and listening comprehension skills in the target foreign language	Interactive case studies, Boomerang method
Improve language skills along with developing transferable skills	Logical thinking and rapid Q&A sessions

Be able to evaluate their progress in developing language skills and demonstrate reflection skills	Preparing and delivering presentations
Possess knowledge, skills, and competencies related to oral speech and listening comprehension practice	Conducting brainstorming sessions and debates Self-assessment and using conceptual charts

From the table, it is clear that the progress in speaking and listening is expected outcomes of this module which can be proven when students achieve B2+ level proficiency according to the Common European Framework of Reference for languages (CEFR). There is no attempt to develop Higher-order competencies such as analytical, evaluative and creativity skills.

References

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2. Nizomiddinovna, S. N., & Maxmurovna, S. B. (2025). Lexical and semantic analysis of antonymic correlated italian proverbs on friendship and love. Web of Scientists and Scholars: Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, 3(3), 21-25.